

Equilibrium magnetization configurations in helical magnets: supplementary material.

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Resume: Here we detail some of the calculations that are not shown in the main body of the work.

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1 Curvilinear form of isotropic exchange.

We need to transform the expression for the isotropic exchange energy density \mathcal{E}_{ex} given by Eq. (6) of the main text that is usually given in cartesian coordinates, into its curvilinear form. Our purpose here is to re-express the components of the magnetization and the gradient operator in terms of their curvilinear counterparts using the relations presented in Sec. II $\nabla \equiv \mathbf{e}_1 \partial_s$ and $m_i = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i \cdot (\mathbf{e}_\alpha m_\alpha)$. after substitution in Eq. (6), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{E}_{\text{ex}} &= (\nabla m_i) (\nabla m_i) \\
 &= (\mathbf{e}_1 \partial_s (m_\alpha \mathbf{e}_\alpha \cdot \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i)) (\mathbf{e}_1 \partial_s (m_\beta \mathbf{e}_\beta \cdot \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i)) \\
 &= (m_\alpha \mathbf{e}_\alpha \cdot \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i)' (m_\beta \mathbf{e}_\beta \cdot \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i)' \\
 &= (m_\alpha \mathbf{e}_\alpha)' \cdot \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i (m_\beta \mathbf{e}_\beta)' \cdot \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i \\
 &= (m_\alpha \mathbf{e}_\alpha)' \cdot (m_\beta \mathbf{e}_\beta)' ,
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where the $'$ denotes derivatives with respect to s .

Expanding the product and making use of the FS formulas to get rid of the derivatives of the FS vectors, this expression separates into 4 different terms

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{E}_{\text{ex}} &= (m_\alpha \mathbf{e}_\alpha)' \cdot (m_\beta \mathbf{e}_\beta)' \\
 &= (m'_\alpha \mathbf{e}_\alpha + m_\alpha \mathbf{e}'_\alpha) \cdot (m'_\beta \mathbf{e}_\beta + m_\beta \mathbf{e}'_\beta) \\
 &= m'_\alpha m'_\beta \mathbf{e}_\alpha \cdot \mathbf{e}_\beta + m'_\alpha m_\beta \mathbf{e}_\alpha \cdot \mathbf{e}'_\beta + m_\alpha m'_\beta \mathbf{e}'_\alpha \cdot \mathbf{e}_\beta \\
 &\quad + m_\alpha m_\beta \mathbf{e}'_\alpha \cdot \mathbf{e}'_\beta \\
 &= m'_\alpha m'_\beta \mathbf{e}_\alpha \cdot \mathbf{e}_\beta + m'_\alpha m_\beta \mathbf{e}_\alpha \cdot \mathcal{F}_{\beta\gamma} \mathbf{e}_\gamma \\
 &\quad + m_\alpha m'_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\alpha\gamma} \mathbf{e}_\gamma \cdot \mathbf{e}_\beta + m_\alpha m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\alpha\gamma} \mathbf{e}_\gamma \cdot \mathcal{F}_{\beta\delta} \mathbf{e}_\delta .
 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

In what follows, we identify the physical meaning of each term separately.

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1.1 Usual isotropic exchange.

The first term in Eq. (2) can be easily understood. Just taking into consideration that the FS frame is an orthonormal basis, it can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{E}_{\text{ex}}^0 &= m'_\alpha m'_\beta \mathbf{e}_\alpha \cdot \mathbf{e}_\beta = m'_\alpha m'_\beta \delta_{\alpha,\beta} \\ &= m'_\alpha m'_\alpha ,\end{aligned}\tag{3}$$

which has the form of the isotropic exchange energy density for a straight wire, but in terms of the FS basis.

1.2 Curvature induced anisotropy

After some operations, the last term in Eq. (2) can be rewritten as follows

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{E}_{\text{ex}}^{\text{A}} &= m_\alpha m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\alpha\gamma} \mathbf{e}_\gamma \cdot \mathcal{F}_{\beta\delta} \mathbf{e}_\delta = m_\alpha m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\alpha\gamma} \mathcal{F}_{\beta\delta} \mathbf{e}_\gamma \cdot \mathbf{e}_\delta \\ &= m_\alpha m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\alpha\gamma} \mathcal{F}_{\beta\delta} \delta_{\gamma,\delta} = m_\alpha m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\alpha\gamma} \mathcal{F}_{\beta\gamma} \\ &\equiv \mathcal{K}_{\alpha\beta} m_\alpha m_\beta ,\end{aligned}\tag{4}$$

where the components of $\mathcal{K}_{\alpha\beta}$ can be computed using the definition of \mathcal{F} in Sec. II as follows

$$\mathcal{K} = \begin{pmatrix} \kappa^2 & 0 & -\kappa\tau \\ 0 & \kappa^2 + \tau^2 & 0 \\ -\kappa\tau & 0 & \tau^2 \end{pmatrix}\tag{5}$$

We see that it has the form of an anisotropy-like interaction induced by curvature effects, with effective anisotropy constants that depend quadratically on τ, κ . In particular, it can be seen that torsion leads to enhanced tangential anisotropy, while κ tilts the magnetization easy-axis towards the binormal direction \mathbf{e}_3 .

1.3 Effective Dzyaloshinskii - Moriya interaction

We are left with two central terms in Eq. (2) that contained crossed products between derivatives and components of the magnetization vector. These will give rise to an antisymmetric interaction because FS transformation matrix is also antisymmetric.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{E}_{\text{ex}}^{\text{DM}} &= m'_\alpha m_\beta \mathbf{e}_\alpha \cdot \mathcal{F}_{\beta\gamma} \mathbf{e}_\gamma + m_\alpha m'_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\alpha\gamma} \mathbf{e}_\gamma \cdot \mathbf{e}_\beta \\ &= m'_\alpha m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\beta\gamma} \mathbf{e}_\alpha \cdot \mathbf{e}_\gamma + m_\alpha m'_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\alpha\gamma} \mathbf{e}_\gamma \cdot \mathbf{e}_\beta \\ &= m'_\alpha m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\beta\gamma} \delta_{\alpha,\gamma} + m_\alpha m'_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\alpha\gamma} \delta_{\gamma,\beta} \\ &= m'_\alpha m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\beta\alpha} + m_\alpha m'_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\alpha\beta} \\ &= -m'_\alpha m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\alpha\beta} + m_\alpha m'_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\alpha\beta} \\ &= \mathcal{F}_{\alpha\beta} (m_\alpha m'_\beta - m'_\alpha m_\beta)\end{aligned}\tag{6}$$

Note this term depends only linearly on the FS transformation matrix components, previously defined in Sec. II and that can be written as a curvature induced effective DM interaction of the form $\mathbf{D} \cdot (\mathbf{m} \times \mathbf{m}')$ with $\mathbf{D} = 2\tau \mathbf{e}_1 + 2\kappa \mathbf{e}_3$ the induced DM vector.

1.4 Angular parametrization of the energy terms

In this section, we particularize the 3 different terms described in the previous subsections using spherical coordinates for the magnetization vector as defined in Eq. (9) of the main text.

1.4.1 Usual isotropic exchange

Recalling Eq. (3) and substituting m_α , we arrive at

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{E}_{\text{ex}}^0 &= m'_\alpha m'_\alpha = (m'_1)^2 + (m'_2)^2 + (m'_3)^2 \\ &= (\cos \theta \theta' \cos \phi - \sin \theta \sin \phi \phi')^2 + (\cos \theta \theta' \sin \phi + \sin \theta \cos \phi \phi')^2 + (-\sin \theta \theta')^2 .\end{aligned}\tag{7}$$

Expanding the last expression and simplifying terms, this equation can be simply rewritten as

$$\mathcal{E}_{\text{ex}}^0 = \theta'^2 + \sin^2 \theta \phi'^2 .\tag{8}$$

1.4.2 Effective anisotropy energy

Starting now from Eq. (4) and writing explicitly m_α , we arrive have

$$\mathcal{E}_{\text{ex}}^{\text{A}} = \mathcal{K}_{\alpha\beta} m_\alpha m_\beta = m_\alpha \mathcal{K}_{\alpha\beta} m_\beta = (\sin \theta \cos \phi \quad \sin \theta \sin \phi \quad \cos \theta)_{[\text{FS}]} \begin{pmatrix} \kappa^2 & 0 & -\kappa\tau \\ 0 & \kappa^2 + \tau^2 & 0 \\ -\kappa\tau & 0 & \tau^2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \sin \theta \cos \phi \\ \sin \theta \sin \phi \\ \cos \theta \end{pmatrix}_{[\text{FS}]} \quad (9)$$

After some tedious algebraic manipulations, one finally finds

$$\mathcal{E}_{\text{ex}}^{\text{A}} = (\kappa \sin \theta - \tau \cos \theta \cos \phi)^2 + \tau^2 \sin^2 \phi \quad (10)$$

1.4.3 Effective Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya interaction

Taking Eq. (6) as a starting point and introducing the angular parametrization of the magnetization

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{E}_{\text{ex}}^{\text{DM}} &= (\sin \theta \cos \phi \quad \sin \theta \sin \phi \quad \cos \theta)_{[\text{FS}]} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \kappa & 0 \\ -\kappa & 0 & \tau \\ 0 & -\tau & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta \theta' \cos \phi - \sin \theta \sin \phi \phi' \\ \cos \theta \theta' \sin \phi + \sin \theta \cos \phi \phi' \\ -\sin \theta \theta' \end{pmatrix}_{[\text{FS}]} \\ &\quad - \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta \theta' \cos \phi - \sin \theta \sin \phi \phi' \\ \cos \theta \theta' \sin \phi + \sin \theta \cos \phi \phi' \\ -\sin \theta \theta' \end{pmatrix}_{[\text{FS}]}^\top \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \kappa & 0 \\ -\kappa & 0 & \tau \\ 0 & -\tau & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \sin \theta \cos \phi \\ \sin \theta \sin \phi \\ \cos \theta \end{pmatrix}_{[\text{FS}]} \quad (11) \end{aligned}$$

Again, managing tedious algebraic manipulations, one finds that the last expression can be written in a compact form as

$$\mathcal{E}_{\text{ex}}^{\text{DM}} = (2\kappa \sin^2 \theta - \tau \sin 2\theta \cos \phi) \phi' - 2\tau \sin \phi \theta' \quad (12)$$

1.4.4 Total energy density

Adding up all three contributions

$$\mathcal{E}_{\text{ex}}^0 = \theta'^2 + \sin^2 \theta \phi'^2 \quad (13)$$

$$\mathcal{E}_{\text{ex}}^{\text{A}} = (\kappa \sin \theta - \tau \cos \theta \cos \phi)^2 + \tau^2 \sin^2 \phi \quad (14)$$

$$\mathcal{E}_{\text{ex}}^{\text{DM}} = (2\kappa \sin^2 \theta - \tau \sin 2\theta \cos \phi) \phi' - 2\tau \sin \phi \theta' , \quad (15)$$

we get finally arrive at

$$\mathcal{E}_{\text{ex}} = \mathcal{E}_{\text{ex}}^0 + \mathcal{E}_{\text{ex}}^{\text{A}} + \mathcal{E}_{\text{ex}}^{\text{DM}} = (\theta' - \tau \sin \phi)^2 + [\sin \theta (\phi' + \kappa) - \tau \cos \theta \cos \phi]^2 , \quad (16)$$

which corresponds to Eq. (10) in the main text.

2 Minimization of the energy functional

In order to find the equations for energy functional minimization, we can use the form of the energy functional discussed in Sec. II., that for the case of tangential anisotropy can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{E} &= \mathcal{S} \int_{\Omega_s} ds \left[\ell^2 \mathcal{E}_{\text{ex}} - |\lambda| \cos^2 \phi \sin^2 \theta \right] \\ &= |\lambda| \mathcal{S} \int_{\Omega_s} ds \left[(\ell^2 / |\lambda|) \mathcal{E}_{\text{ex}} - \cos^2 \phi \sin^2 \theta \right] \\ &= |\lambda| \mathcal{S} \int_{\Omega_s} ds \left[w^2 \mathcal{E}_{\text{ex}} - \cos^2 \phi \sin^2 \theta \right] , \quad (17) \end{aligned}$$

where we have introduced the magnetic characteristic length $w = \ell / \sqrt{|\lambda|}$. Now, since s does not parametrize the space domain of the wire, we make a change of variable $\chi = s/\tilde{s}$, so that we get

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{E} &= |\lambda| \mathcal{S} \tilde{s} \int_{\Omega_s} \frac{ds}{\tilde{s}} \left[w^2 \mathcal{E}_{\text{ex}} - \cos^2 \phi \sin^2 \theta \right] \\ &= |\lambda| \mathcal{S} \tilde{s} \int_{\Omega_\chi} d\chi \left[w^2 \mathcal{E}_{\text{ex}} - \cos^2 \phi \sin^2 \theta \right] \\ &\equiv |\lambda| \mathcal{S} \tilde{s} \tilde{\mathcal{E}} , \quad (18) \end{aligned}$$

where we have defined $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}$ as

$$\tilde{\mathcal{E}} = \int_{\Omega_\chi} d\chi \underbrace{\left[w^2 \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{\bar{s}} \partial_\chi \theta - \tau \sin \phi \right)^2 + \left(\sin \theta \left(\frac{1}{\bar{s}} \partial_\chi \phi + \kappa \right) - \tau \cos \theta \cos \phi \right)^2 \right\} - \cos^2 \phi \sin^2 \theta \right]}_{\mathcal{L}(\theta, \partial_\chi \theta, \phi, \partial_\chi \phi)} \quad (19)$$

We are now left with the task of computing the functional derivatives of $\tilde{\mathcal{E}}$. This can be done using the formal definition of a functional derivative given by

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \theta} - \frac{\partial}{\partial \chi} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial (\partial_\chi \theta)} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \phi} - \frac{\partial}{\partial \chi} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial (\partial_\chi \phi)} = 0. \quad (20)$$

Performing the corresponding derivatives in (19), we obtain the following set of differential equations

$$w^2 \left\{ -2 \left(\frac{1}{\bar{s}^2} \partial_\chi^2 \theta - \tau \cos \phi \frac{1}{\bar{s}} \partial_\chi \phi \right) + 2 \left(\sin \theta \left(\frac{1}{\bar{s}} \partial_\chi \phi + \kappa \right) - \tau \cos \theta \cos \phi \right) \times \right. \\ \left. \times \left(\cos \theta \left(\frac{1}{\bar{s}} \partial_\chi \phi + \kappa \right) + \tau \sin \theta \cos \theta \right) \right\} - 2 \cos^2 \phi \sin \theta \cos \theta = 0 \quad (21)$$

$$w^2 \left\{ -2 \left(\frac{1}{\bar{s}} \partial_\chi \theta - \tau \sin \phi \right) \tau \cos \phi - 2 \cos \theta \frac{1}{\bar{s}} \partial_\chi \theta \left[\sin \theta \left(\frac{1}{\bar{s}} \partial_\chi \phi + \kappa \right) - \tau \cos \theta \cos \phi \right] \right. \\ \left. - 2 \sin \theta \left[\cos \theta \frac{1}{\bar{s}} \partial_\chi \theta \left(\frac{1}{\bar{s}} \partial_\chi \phi + \kappa \right) + \sin \theta \frac{1}{\bar{s}^2} \partial_\chi^2 \phi + \tau \sin \theta \frac{1}{\bar{s}} \partial_\chi \theta \cos \phi + \tau \cos \theta \sin \phi \frac{1}{\bar{s}} \partial_\chi \phi \right] \right. \\ \left. + 2 \tau \cos \theta \sin \phi \left(\sin \theta \left(\frac{1}{\bar{s}} \partial_\chi \phi + \kappa \right) - \tau \cos \theta \cos \phi \right) \right\} + 2 \cos \phi \sin \phi \sin^2 \theta = 0 \quad (22)$$

Taking the inverse change of variable and rearrange terms, we find the differential equations governing $\theta(s)$ and $\phi(s)$ given by Eq. (14), (15) of the main text.

3 Curvilinear form of the intrinsic Dzyaloshinskii-Moriya interaction

Although in the main text we have not considered materials with intrinsic DMI, in this last section we would like to show how the curvature of the wire affects the contribution of this kind of interactions, similarly to what we have done for the exchange interaction. In particular, we will show that a biaxial anisotropy emerges as a consequence of curvature.

The intrinsic DMI contribution to the micromagnetic total energy functional is given by

$$\mathcal{E}_{\text{DMI}} = -\mathcal{I} \int ds \mathcal{D} \cdot [\mathbf{m}(s) \times \partial_s \mathbf{m}(s)] . \quad (23)$$

So that we can define the intrinsic DMI energy density as

$$\mathcal{E}_{\text{DMI}}^{\text{DMI}} = \mathcal{D} \cdot [\mathbf{m}(s) \times \partial_s \mathbf{m}(s)] \quad (24)$$

where \mathcal{D} is the intrinsic DMI interaction vector. We express now the magnetization $\mathbf{m}(s)$ in the curvilinear frame as we have already done for the exchange interaction previously:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{E}_{\text{DMI}}^{\text{DMI}} &= \mathcal{D} \cdot (m_\alpha \mathbf{e}_\alpha \times \partial_s (m_\beta \mathbf{e}_\beta)) = \mathcal{D} \cdot (m_\alpha \mathbf{e}_\alpha \times (m'_\beta \mathbf{e}_\beta + m_\beta \mathbf{e}'_\beta)) \\ &= \mathcal{D} \cdot (m_\alpha \mathbf{e}_\alpha \times m'_\beta \mathbf{e}_\beta + m_\alpha \mathbf{e}_\alpha \times m_\beta \mathbf{e}'_\beta) \\ &= \mathcal{D} \cdot (m_\alpha \mathbf{e}_\alpha \times m'_\beta \mathbf{e}_\beta + m_\alpha \mathbf{e}_\alpha \times m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\beta\gamma} \mathbf{e}_\gamma) \\ &= \mathcal{D} \cdot (m_\alpha m_\beta \mathbf{e}_\alpha \times \mathbf{e}_\beta + m_\alpha m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\beta\gamma} \mathbf{e}_\alpha \times \mathbf{e}_\gamma) \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

Since we can also express the intrinsic DMI vector in the F-S basis as $\mathcal{D} = \mathcal{D}_\delta \mathbf{e}_\delta$, the last equation can be written as the sum of the two following terms

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{E}^{\text{DMI}} &= \mathcal{D}_\delta \mathbf{e}_\delta \cdot (m_\alpha m_\beta \mathbf{e}_\alpha \times \mathbf{e}_\beta + m_\alpha m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\beta\gamma} \mathbf{e}_\alpha \times \mathbf{e}_\gamma) \\ &= \underbrace{\mathcal{D}_\delta m_\alpha m'_\beta \mathbf{e}_\delta \cdot (\mathbf{e}_\alpha \times \mathbf{e}_\beta)}_{\mathcal{A}} + \underbrace{\mathcal{D}_\delta m_\alpha m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\beta\gamma} \mathbf{e}_\delta \cdot (\mathbf{e}_\alpha \times \mathbf{e}_\gamma)}_{\mathcal{B}}. \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

Note now that, the first term \mathcal{A} , has the form of an antisymmetric interaction as the cross products change sign if subindices are permuted, while the second, \mathcal{B} , corresponds to a symmetric interaction since, apart from the cross product, the antisymmetric F-S tensor is also involved.

3.1 Intrinsic DMI antisymmetric contribution

For the antisymmetric contribution to the DMI energy, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A} &\equiv \mathcal{D}_\delta m_\alpha m'_\beta \mathbf{e}_\delta \cdot (\mathbf{e}_\alpha \times \mathbf{e}_\beta) \\ &= \mathcal{D}_1 m_\alpha m'_\beta \mathbf{e}_1 \cdot (\mathbf{e}_\alpha \times \mathbf{e}_\beta) + \mathcal{D}_2 m_\alpha m'_\beta \mathbf{e}_2 \cdot (\mathbf{e}_\alpha \times \mathbf{e}_\beta) + \mathcal{D}_3 m_\alpha m'_\beta \mathbf{e}_3 \cdot (\mathbf{e}_\alpha \times \mathbf{e}_\beta) \\ &\equiv \mathcal{A}^1 + \mathcal{A}^2 + \mathcal{A}^3 \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

Notice that, in order to calculate the sums over α, β in \mathcal{A}^1 , the only terms that contribute are those for which $\mathbf{e}_1 \cdot (\mathbf{e}_\alpha \times \mathbf{e}_\beta) \neq 0$ for any $\alpha, \beta = 1, 2, 3$, so we need that the cross product is either \mathbf{e}_1 or $-\mathbf{e}_1$. In this way, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}^1 &= \mathcal{D}_1 m_\alpha m'_\beta \mathbf{e}_1 \cdot (\mathbf{e}_\alpha \times \mathbf{e}_\beta) = \mathcal{D}_1 m_2 m'_3 \mathbf{e}_1 \cdot (\mathbf{e}_2 \times \mathbf{e}_3) + \mathcal{D}_1 m_3 m'_2 \mathbf{e}_1 \cdot (\mathbf{e}_3 \times \mathbf{e}_2) \\ &= \mathcal{D}_1 \mathbf{e}_1 \cdot (\mathbf{e}_2 \times \mathbf{e}_3) (m_2 m'_3 - m_3 m'_2) \\ &= \mathcal{D}_1 (m_2 m'_3 - m_3 m'_2). \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

We can proceed similarly for the other two terms to find

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}^2 &= \mathcal{D}_2 m_\alpha m'_\beta \mathbf{e}_2 \cdot (\mathbf{e}_\alpha \times \mathbf{e}_\beta) = \mathcal{D}_2 m_1 m'_3 \mathbf{e}_2 \cdot (\mathbf{e}_1 \times \mathbf{e}_3) + \mathcal{D}_2 m_3 m'_1 \mathbf{e}_2 \cdot (\mathbf{e}_3 \times \mathbf{e}_1) \\ &= -\mathcal{D}_2 \mathbf{e}_2 \cdot (\mathbf{e}_3 \times \mathbf{e}_1) (m_1 m'_3 - m_3 m'_1) \\ &= -\mathcal{D}_2 (m_1 m'_3 - m_3 m'_1), \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}^3 &= \mathcal{D}_3 m_\alpha m'_\beta \mathbf{e}_3 \cdot (\mathbf{e}_\alpha \times \mathbf{e}_\beta) = \mathcal{D}_3 m_1 m'_2 \mathbf{e}_3 \cdot (\mathbf{e}_1 \times \mathbf{e}_2) + \mathcal{D}_3 m_2 m'_1 \mathbf{e}_3 \cdot (\mathbf{e}_2 \times \mathbf{e}_1) \\ &= \mathcal{D}_3 \mathbf{e}_3 \cdot (\mathbf{e}_1 \times \mathbf{e}_2) (m_1 m'_2 - m_2 m'_1) \\ &= \mathcal{D}_3 (m_1 m'_2 - m_2 m'_1). \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

Finally, we obtain the following expression for \mathcal{A}

$$\mathcal{A} \equiv \mathcal{A}^1 + \mathcal{A}^2 + \mathcal{A}^3 = \mathcal{D}_1 (m_2 m'_3 - m_3 m'_2) - \mathcal{D}_2 (m_1 m'_3 - m_3 m'_1) + \mathcal{D}_3 (m_1 m'_2 - m_2 m'_1). \quad (31)$$

Notice that the last expression preserves the form of a usual DMI interaction $\mathcal{A} \equiv \tilde{\mathcal{D}}_{\alpha\beta} (m_\alpha m'_\beta - m_\beta m'_\alpha)$, where $\tilde{\mathcal{D}}_{\alpha\beta}$ is the antisymmetric tensor given by

$$\tilde{\mathcal{D}} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -\mathcal{D}_3/2 & \mathcal{D}_2/2 \\ \mathcal{D}_3/2 & 0 & -\mathcal{D}_1/2 \\ -\mathcal{D}_2/2 & \mathcal{D}_1/2 & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (32)$$

Notice that the tensor components have been divided by 2 in order to avoid double counting and the change of the sign in \mathcal{A} to take into account the sign in equation Eq. (23).

3.2 Intrinsic DMI effective symmetric interaction

Following a similar procedure, we can arrive at a closed expression for the symmetric term of Eq. (26).

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{B} &\equiv \mathcal{D}_\delta m_\alpha m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\beta\gamma} \mathbf{e}_\delta \cdot (\mathbf{e}_\alpha \times \mathbf{e}_\gamma) \\
&= \mathcal{D}_1 m_\alpha m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\beta\gamma} \mathbf{e}_1 \cdot (\mathbf{e}_\alpha \times \mathbf{e}_\gamma) + \mathcal{D}_2 m_\alpha m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\beta\gamma} \mathbf{e}_2 \cdot (\mathbf{e}_\alpha \times \mathbf{e}_\gamma) + \mathcal{D}_3 m_\alpha m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\beta\gamma} \mathbf{e}_3 \cdot (\mathbf{e}_\alpha \times \mathbf{e}_\gamma) \\
&\equiv \mathcal{B}^1 + \mathcal{B}^2 + \mathcal{B}^3
\end{aligned} \tag{33}$$

Taking into account the comments made for the calculation of the different terms in \mathcal{A} , we can compute the 3 terms, leading to

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{B}^1 &= \mathcal{D}_1 m_\alpha m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\beta\gamma} \mathbf{e}_1 \cdot (\mathbf{e}_\alpha \times \mathbf{e}_\gamma) = \mathcal{D}_1 m_2 m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\beta 3} \mathbf{e}_1 \cdot (\mathbf{e}_2 \times \mathbf{e}_3) + \mathcal{D}_1 m_3 m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\beta 2} \mathbf{e}_1 \cdot (\mathbf{e}_3 \times \mathbf{e}_2) \\
&= \mathcal{D}_1 m_2 m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\beta 3} - \mathcal{D}_1 m_3 m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\beta 2} \\
&= \mathcal{D}_1 m_2 (m_1 \mathcal{F}_{13} + m_2 \mathcal{F}_{23} + m_3 \mathcal{F}_{33}) - \mathcal{D}_1 m_3 (m_1 \mathcal{F}_{12} + m_2 \mathcal{F}_{22} + m_3 \mathcal{F}_{32}) \\
&= \mathcal{D}_1 m_2 (\tau m_2) - \mathcal{D}_1 m_3 (\kappa m_1 - \tau m_3) \\
&= \mathcal{D}_1 (\tau m_2^2 - \kappa m_3 m_1 + \tau m_3^2)
\end{aligned} \tag{34}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{B}^2 &= \mathcal{D}_2 m_\alpha m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\beta\gamma} \mathbf{e}_2 \cdot (\mathbf{e}_\alpha \times \mathbf{e}_\gamma) = \mathcal{D}_2 m_1 m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\beta 3} \mathbf{e}_2 \cdot (\mathbf{e}_1 \times \mathbf{e}_3) + \mathcal{D}_2 m_3 m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\beta 1} \mathbf{e}_2 \cdot (\mathbf{e}_3 \times \mathbf{e}_1) \\
&= -\mathcal{D}_2 m_1 m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\beta 3} + \mathcal{D}_2 m_3 m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\beta 1} \\
&= -\mathcal{D}_2 m_1 (m_1 \mathcal{F}_{13} + m_2 \mathcal{F}_{23} + m_3 \mathcal{F}_{33}) + \mathcal{D}_2 m_3 (m_1 \mathcal{F}_{11} + m_2 \mathcal{F}_{21} + m_3 \mathcal{F}_{31}) \\
&= -\mathcal{D}_2 m_1 (\tau m_2) + \mathcal{D}_2 m_3 (-\kappa m_2) \\
&= -\mathcal{D}_2 (\tau m_1 m_2 + \kappa m_3 m_2)
\end{aligned} \tag{35}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{B}^3 &= \mathcal{D}_3 m_\alpha m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\beta\gamma} \mathbf{e}_3 \cdot (\mathbf{e}_\alpha \times \mathbf{e}_\gamma) = \mathcal{D}_3 m_1 m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\beta 2} \mathbf{e}_3 \cdot (\mathbf{e}_1 \times \mathbf{e}_2) + \mathcal{D}_3 m_2 m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\beta 1} \mathbf{e}_3 \cdot (\mathbf{e}_2 \times \mathbf{e}_1) \\
&= \mathcal{D}_3 m_1 m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\beta 2} - \mathcal{D}_3 m_2 m_\beta \mathcal{F}_{\beta 1} \\
&= \mathcal{D}_3 m_1 (m_1 \mathcal{F}_{12} + m_2 \mathcal{F}_{22} + m_3 \mathcal{F}_{32}) - \mathcal{D}_3 m_2 (m_1 \mathcal{F}_{11} + m_2 \mathcal{F}_{21} + m_3 \mathcal{F}_{31}) \\
&= \mathcal{D}_3 m_1 (\kappa m_1 - \tau m_3) - \mathcal{D}_3 m_2 (-\kappa m_2) \\
&= \mathcal{D}_3 (\kappa m_1^2 - \tau m_1 m_3 + \kappa m_2^2)
\end{aligned} \tag{36}$$

Finally, adding up the 3 contributions we are lead to

$$\mathcal{B} \equiv \mathcal{B}^1 + \mathcal{B}^2 + \mathcal{B}^3 = \mathcal{D}_1 (\tau m_2^2 - \kappa m_3 m_1 + \tau m_3^2) - \mathcal{D}_2 (\tau m_1 m_2 + \kappa m_3 m_2) + \mathcal{D}_3 (\kappa m_1^2 - \tau m_1 m_3 + \kappa m_2^2). \tag{37}$$

We can use now the normalization condition of the magnetization $|\mathbf{m}(s)| = 1$ to express $m_1^2 + m_2^2 + m_3^2 = 1$ so that $m_2^2 = 1 - m_1^2 - m_3^2$ and then rewrite

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{B} &= \kappa \mathcal{D}_3 m_1^2 + (\tau \mathcal{D}_1 + \kappa \mathcal{D}_3) m_2^2 + \tau \mathcal{D}_1 m_3^2 - \tau \mathcal{D}_2 m_1 m_2 - (\kappa \mathcal{D}_1 + \tau \mathcal{D}_3) m_1 m_3 - \kappa \mathcal{D}_2 m_2 m_3 \\
&= \kappa \mathcal{D}_3 m_1^2 + (\tau \mathcal{D}_1 + \kappa \mathcal{D}_3) (1 - m_1^2 - m_3^2) + \tau \mathcal{D}_1 m_3^2 - \tau \mathcal{D}_2 m_1 m_2 - (\kappa \mathcal{D}_1 + \tau \mathcal{D}_3) m_1 m_3 - \kappa \mathcal{D}_2 m_2 m_3 \\
&= -\tau \mathcal{D}_1 m_1^2 - \kappa \mathcal{D}_3 m_3^2 + (\tau \mathcal{D}_1 + \kappa \mathcal{D}_3) - \tau \mathcal{D}_2 m_1 m_2 - (\kappa \mathcal{D}_1 + \tau \mathcal{D}_3) m_1 m_3 - \kappa \mathcal{D}_2 m_2 m_3
\end{aligned} \tag{38}$$

The constant term $\tau \mathcal{D}_1 + \kappa \mathcal{D}_3$ can be disregarded as it only shifts the total energy. Note now that we can write down $\mathcal{B} \equiv \tilde{\mathcal{K}}_{\alpha\beta} m_\alpha m_\beta$, where $\tilde{\mathcal{K}}_{\alpha\beta}$ is a symmetric tensor given by

$$\tilde{\mathcal{K}} = \begin{pmatrix} \tau \mathcal{D}_1 & \frac{\tau \mathcal{D}_2}{2} & \frac{\kappa \mathcal{D}_1 + \tau \mathcal{D}_3}{2} \\ \frac{\tau \mathcal{D}_2}{2} & 0 & \frac{\kappa \mathcal{D}_2}{2} \\ \frac{\kappa \mathcal{D}_1 + \tau \mathcal{D}_3}{2} & \frac{\kappa \mathcal{D}_2}{2} & \kappa \mathcal{D}_3 \end{pmatrix}. \tag{39}$$

We conclude that if DMI interaction is relevant in our material, it induces an effective anisotropy given by \mathcal{B} that due to the curvature and geometry of the magnetic system. The intrinsic DMI term has to be added to the extrinsic DMI term coming from the exchange interaction.